

Comparison of plant species indices under wildlife and livestock grazing site

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Abstract

Vegetation changes in terms of specific plant or family can determine vegetation composition, rangeland condition, grazing pressure and herbivores food preference. Therefore, it can be a base for ecosystem planning and rangelands management. This research tried to compares some of plant species indices between two regions under livestock and wildlife grazing in Kalmand-Bahadoran plain rangelands of Yazd province. For this purpose, in the first step two areas of Kalmand-Bahadoran plain rangelands of Yazd province were selected. Sampling was done using random-systematic method. In each plot and along each transect, species names, families, their presence and absence, canopy cover percentage, production and density for each species were noted. The results showed that in livestock grazing site, the dominant species (*Artemisia sieberi*), *Stipa barbata* ($p < 0.01$) and *Scorzonera* sp. Canopy cover ($p < 0.05$) increased significantly, while *Colchicum kotschyi*, *Iris songarica* ($p < 0.05$) and *Stachys inflata* canopy cover ($p < 0.01$) decreased. In deer grazing area, in terms of production and density, some species like *Stachys inflata*, *Colchicum kotschyi*, *Aegopordon berardioides* and *Boissiera squarrosa* ($p < 0.01$) had significantly increased in comparison to livestock grazing area but *Stipa barbata* and *Scorzonera* sp. ($p < 0.05$) raised significantly in livestock grazing site. According to results, it is necessary to recognize all vegetation aspects in rangelands specially plant species indices in order to proper grazing management and decide for future restoration planning.

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Introduction

Rangelands consist of different plant species with distinctive life forms and growth characteristics, which have a specific grazing value (Ahmadi *et al.*, 2009). Plant species have different Strategies and this causes their more resistance to grazing. Changes in vegetation indices in terms of specific plant or family can determine vegetation composition, rangeland condition, grazing pressure and herbivores food preference. Therefore, it can be a base for ecosystem planning and rangelands management. There are several studies about grazing effects on plant species characteristics. Some researches revealed a significant increase about production and density of some species such as *Stipa barbata*, *Artemisia sieberi*, *Astragalus sp.* *salsola sp.* and also *Scorzonera sp.* canopy cover (Akbarzadeh, 2005; Aghajanlou & Moosavi, 2006; Akbarzadeh *et al.*, 2007; Baghestani Meybodi *et al.*, 2007) under livestock grazing. Other studies showed that canopy cover percentage, production and density of the species like *Echinops sp.* *Bromus sp.* *Boissiera squarrosa*, *Onobrychis sp.* and *Scariola orientalis* increased significantly in the regions with more livestock grazing pressure (Firinioglu *et al.*, 2007; Jalilvand *et al.*, 2007; Heidarian Aghakhani *et al.*, 2010; Imani *et al.*, 2010). Eftekhari *et al.* (2009) announced that the species *Stachys inflata* canopy cover and production has increased in deer grazing site.

In most parts of the world livestock grazing is the most common use of rangelands, and this is the main factor of rangelands degradation and extinction of wildlife (When *et al.*, 2011; Pellerin *et al.*, 2006). Wildlife and livestock cause changes on rangeland plant species and vegetation (Cesa & Paruelo, 2011; Jeddi & Chaieb, 2010). In arid rangelands in many parts of the world, identifying vegetation characteristics changes under wildlife and livestock grazing is the most important basic study to find a correct way for range management (Manier & Hobbs, 2007; Moser & Witmer, 2000; Hossein Jafari *et al.*, 2013).

According to the literature reviews, there is a little information about wildlife and livestock grazing effects on plant species indices.

Most studies have focused on vegetation characteristics totally but they didn't investigate particular plant species properties.

This study tries to find degradation effects of livestock on specific plant species characteristics in an arid ecosystem. So, the purpose of this study is to compare plant species indices such as canopy cover percentage, production and density between wildlife (deer) and livestock (sheep and goat) grazing sites. The results can be applied in restoration programs to choose particular plants in each kind of grazing management.

Materials and methods

Study site

Kalmand-Bahadoran plain is located southeast of Yazd province and at 31°20' north latitude and 54°30' east longitude. Plain areas cover most of the region and the rest composed of impassable height, mountains and hills. The average altitude is 1616 meters above sea level. Maximum and minimum heights in the region are 3290 m and 1400 m respectively. The averages of maximum and minimum temperatures are respectively 44.29°C and 22.5°C. The average annual precipitation is about 77 mm and the mean annual moisture is 30% (Karimian, 1999).

Methodology

After determining the study area using topographic maps (1:50000), during field investigation, two regions were chose, one in the protected area under wildlife grazing (deer) and the other outside that area under livestock grazing (sheep and goat).

The two regions are flat; their climatic and topographic conditions are the same (Consulting engineers of Iran, 2002; Alikhani & Ahmadi, 2012).

Sampling was done using random systematic method. Depending on vegetation type and condition (Mesdaghi, 2003), 10 transects of 100 m randomly and 3 plots of 2 m² were placed on each transect using systematic method in each site. In each plot and along each transect, species names, families, their presence and absence,

canopy cover percentage, production and density for each species were noted. Data processing and analysis related to plant species indices between the two study regions were performed using SPSS16 software (independent sample t-test analysis).

Results

During sampling, 27 plant species of 10 families are found in the region under wildlife grazing. 25 species which belong to 10 families were identified in livestock grazing site. These species have different life and biologic forms (Table 1).

Table 1. Species presence and absence list in two wildlife and livestock grazing sites related to sampling.

Species name	Family	Longevity	Life form	Biologic form	Livestock	Wildlife
<i>Acantholimon</i> sp.	Plumbaginaceae	P	Shrub	Ch	-	+
<i>Aegopordon berardioides</i>	Compositae	P	Forb	He	-	+
<i>Aellenia subaphylla</i>	Chenopodiaceae	P	Shrub	Ch	+	-
<i>Artemisia sieberi</i>	Compositae	P	Shrub	Ch	+	+
<i>Astragalus glauca canthus</i>	Papilionaceae	P	Shrub	Ph	+	+
<i>Astragalus microphysa</i>	Papilionaceae	P	Shrub	Ch	-	+
<i>Astragalus</i> sp.	Papilionaceae	P	Shrub	Ch	+	+
<i>Atraphaxis spinosa</i>	Polygonaceae	P	Shrub	Ch	+	-
<i>Boissiera squarrosa</i>	Gramineae	A	Grass	Th	+	+
<i>Centaurea</i> sp.	Compositae	A	Forb	Th	+	+
<i>Cirsium</i> sp.	Compositae	P	Forb	He	+	+
<i>Colchicum kotschyi</i>	Liliaceae	P	Forb	Ge	+	+
<i>Convolvulus virgatus</i>	Convolvulaceae	P	Shrub	Ph	-	+
<i>Cornulaca leucacantha</i>	Chenopodiaceae	P	Shrub	Ch	-	+
<i>Cornulaca monacantha</i>	Chenopodiaceae	P	Shrub	Ch	+	-
<i>Cousinia deserti</i>	Compositae	P	Shrub	Ch	+	+
<i>Cyperus</i> sp.	Cyperaceae	P	Forb	Ge	+	-
<i>Echinops</i> sp.	Compositae	P	Shrub	He	+	-
<i>Euphorbia helioscopia</i>	Euphorbiaceae	A	Forb	He	+	-
<i>Gymnocarpus decander</i>	Caryophyllaceae	P	Bush-tree	Ph	+	-
<i>Heliotropium</i> sp.	Boraginaceae	P	Shrub	Ch	-	+
<i>Iris songarica</i>	Iridaceae	P	Forb	He	+	+
<i>Jurinea radians</i>	Compositae	P	Shrub	Ch	-	+
<i>Lactuca</i> sp.	Compositae	P	Shrub	Ch	+	+
<i>Launea acantodes</i>	Compositae	P	Shrub	He	+	+
<i>Lolium rigidum</i>	Gramineae	A	Grass	Th	-	+
<i>Noea mucronata</i>	Chenopodiaceae	P	Shrub	Ch	-	+
<i>Paracaryum persicum</i>	Boraginaceae	A	Forb	Th	-	+
<i>Peganum harmala</i>	Zygophyllaceae	P	Forb	He	+	-
<i>Salsola tomentosa</i>	Chenopodiaceae	P	Shrub	Ch	+	-
<i>Scariola orientalis</i>	Compositae	P	Shrub	Ch	+	+
<i>Scorzonera</i> sp.	Compositae	P	Forb	Ge	+	+
<i>Scrophularia steriata</i>	Scrophulariaceae	P	Shrub	Ch	-	+
<i>Stachys inflata</i>	Lamiaceae	P	Shrub	Ch	-	+
<i>Stipa barbata</i>	Gramineae	P	Grass	He	+	+
<i>Ziziphora tenuir</i>	Lamiaceae	A	Forb	Th	+	+
<i>Zygophyllum euryptherum</i>	Zygophyllaceae	P	Bush-tree	Ph	+	-

(Ch= Chamophyt, He= Hemicriptophyt, Ph= Phanerophyt, Th= Therophyt).

Among 13 plant families in sampling plots, Scrophulariaceae,

Boraginaceae and Convolvulaceae exist only in deer grazing site. On the other side,

families such as Zygophyllaceae, Polygonaceae and Euphorbiaceae were found in livestock grazing site and 7 plant families were in both sites. The results show that Lamiaceae ($p < 0.01$),

Liliaceae and Iridaceae ($p < 0.05$) in wildlife grazing site and Compositeae ($p < 0.01$) and Gramineae families ($p < 0.05$) in livestock site increased significantly (table2).

Table 2. Comparing families with the most canopy cover percentages in study sites using independent sample t-test.

Families	Treatment	Average	Sd	df	t
Chenopodiaceae	wildlife	0.06	0.08	58	1.004 ^{ns}
	Livestock	0.11	0.13		
Compositeae	wildlife	8.66	2.05	58	**4.119-
	Livestock	12.10	1.67		
Gramineae	wildlife	0.34	0.18	58	*2.552-
	Livestock	0.58	0.22		
Iridaceae	wildlife	0.66	0.34	58	*2.300
	Livestock	0.25	0.45		
Lamiaceae	wildlife	2.05	1.06	58	**6.082
	Livestock	0.02	0.03		
Liliaceae	wildlife	0.18	0.18	58	*2.229
	Livestock	0.05	0.06		
Papilionaceae	wildlife	0.78	0.50	58	^{ns} 1.107 ^{ns}
	Livestock	0.59	0.21		

** : $p < 0.01$, (* : $p < 0.05$), ()^{ns}: No significant.

The results of comparing the species with the most canopy cover percentage in sampling plots indicate that there is no difference.

Between the two regions in terms of species canopy cover percentage like *Noea mucronata*, *Aegopordon berardioides*, *Boissiera squarrosa*, *Astragalus* sp. and *Lactuca* sp. The species *Colchicum kotschyi*, *Iris songarica* ($p < 0.05$) and *Stachys inflata* ($p < 0.01$) reveal a significant increase in deer grazing site, but some species such as *Artemisia sieberi*, *Stipa barbata* ($p < 0.01$) and *Scorzonera* sp. ($p < 0.05$) indicate a significant reduction in deer

grazing site compared to livestock grazing site (table3).

The results show a significant increase in relation to *Colchicum kotschyi*, *Stachys inflata* and *Boissiera squarrosa* in deer grazing site ($p < 0.01$), while the species production like *Aegopordon berardioides* ($p < 0.01$), *Stipa barbata* and *Scorzonera* sp. ($p < 0.05$) has increased significantly in livestock grazing area. There is no difference between the two study areas related to the species production such as *Noea mucronata*, *Iris songarica*, *Artemisia sieberi*, *Astragalus* sp. and *Lactuca* sp. (Table 4).

Table 3. Comparing species with the most canopy cover percentages in study sites using independent sample t-test.

Species	Treatment	Canopy cover percentage	Sd	df	t
<i>Noea mucronata</i>	Wildlife	2.04	0.59	58	0.863 ^{ns}
	Livestock	1.79	0.68		
<i>Colchicum kotschyi</i>	Wildlife	0.185	0.181	58	*2.229
	Livestock	0.050	0.062		
<i>Iris songarica</i>	Wildlife	0.660	0.336	58	*2.300
	Livestock	0.250	0.453		
<i>Artemisia sieberi</i>	Wildlife	5.065	1.608	58	** - 4.729
	Livestock	7.915	1.022		
<i>Stachys inflata</i>	Wildlife	2.055	1.059	58	**6.135

Species	Treatment	Canopy cover percentage	Sd	df	t
<i>Stipa barbata</i>	Livestock	0.003	0.003		
	Wildlife	0.020	0.042	58	**_
<i>Aegopordon berardioides</i>	Livestock	0.185	0.111		4.405
	Wildlife	0.003	0.004	58	- 1.964 ^{ns}
<i>Boissiera squarrosa</i>	Livestock	0.02	0.02		
	Wildlife	0.320	0.173	58	- 0.961 ^{ns}
<i>Astragalus sp.</i>	Livestock	0.395	0.175		
	Wildlife	0.240	0.227	58	0.915 ^{ns}
<i>Scorzonera sp.</i>	Livestock	0.155	0.186		
	Wildlife	0.270	0.111	58	* - 2.846
<i>Lactuca sp.</i>	Livestock	0.510	0.242		
	Wildlife	1.485	1.241	58	0.142 ^{ns}
	Livestock	1.420	0.740		

** : p<0.01), (**: p<0.05)(,)^{ns}: No significant.

Table 4. Comparing species with the most production in study sites using independent sample t-test.

Species	Treatment	Production	Sd	df	t
<i>Noea mucronata</i>	Wildlife	0.18	1.01	58	0.949 ^{ns}
	Livestock	0.01	0.04		
<i>Colchicum kotschyi</i>	Wildlife	0.39	0.41	58	3.639 ^{**}
	Livestock	0.07	0.23		
<i>Iris songarica</i>	Wildlife	1.84	4.68	58	0.685 ^{ns}
	Livestock	0.96	5.19		
<i>Artemisia sieberi</i>	Wildlife	24.71	20.31	58	0.411 ^{ns}
	Livestock	22.73	16.92		
<i>Stachys inflata</i>	Wildlife	9.11	8.18	58	6.088 ^{**}
	Livestock	0.02	0.06		
<i>Stipa barbata</i>	Wildlife	0.01	0.03	58	- 2.371 [*]
	Livestock	0.23	0.52		
<i>Aegopordon berardioides</i>	Wildlife	0.01	0.06	58	-3.160 ^{**}
	Livestock	0.23	0.37		
<i>Boissiera squarrosa</i>	Wildlife	0.74	0.53	58	4.748 ^{**}
	Livestock	0.23	0.25		
<i>Astragalus sp.</i>	Wildlife	0.02	0.06	58	.987 ^{ns}
	Livestock	0.003	0.007		
<i>Scorzonera sp.</i>	Wildlife	1.00	1.10	58	- 2.109 [*]
	Livestock	1.66	1.30		
<i>Lactuca sp.</i>	Wildlife	3.89	6.42	58	1.017 ^{ns}
	Livestock	2.45	4.37		

** : p<0.01), (**: p<0.05)(,)^{ns}: No significant.

Comparing the species with the most density in two regions indicate that the species density like *Colchicum kotschyi*, *Stachys inflata* and *Boissiera squarrosa* raise in deer grazing site (p<0.01), but *Aegopordon berardioides* (p<0.01).

Stipa barbata and *Scorzonera sp.* (p<0.05) increase significantly in livestock grazing site. There is no significant difference between two sites in terms of species density such as *Noea mucronata*, *Iris songarica*, *Artemisia sieberi*, *Astragalus sp.* and *Lactuca sp.*

Table 5. Comparing species with the most density in study sites using independent sample t-test

Species	Treatment	Density	Sd	df	t
<i>Noea mucronata</i>	Wildlife	0.10	0.20	58	0.684 ^{ns}
	Livestock	0.07	0.17		
<i>Colchicum kotschyi</i>	Wildlife	0.47	0.54	58	3.762 ^{**}
	Livestock	0.07	0.22		
<i>Iris songarica</i>	Wildlife	2.77	7.28	58	1.357 ^{ns}
	Livestock	0.72	3.92		
<i>Artemisia sieberi</i>	Wildlife	1.07	0.80	58	- 0.324 ^{ns}
	Livestock	1.13	0.80		
<i>Stachys inflata</i>	Wildlife	0.95	0.88	58	^{**} 5.494
	Livestock	0.05	0.15		
<i>Stipa barbata</i>	Wildlife	0.02	0.09	58	* - 2.397
	Livestock	0.23	0.49		
<i>Aegopordon berardioides</i>	Wildlife	0.03	0.13	58	^{**} 2.925-
	Livestock	0.40	0.67		
<i>Boissiera squarrosa</i>	Wildlife	12.97	8.75	58	5.500 ^{**}
	Livestock	3.50	3.51		
<i>Astragalus sp.</i>	Wildlife	0.03	0.18	58	1.985 ^{ns}
	Livestock	0.002	0.01		
<i>Scorzonera sp.</i>	Wildlife	2.03	2.43	58	*2.346-
	Livestock	3.65	2.89		
<i>Lactuca sp.</i>	Wildlife	0.30	0.50	58	0.294 ^{ns}
	Livestock	0.27	0.36		

** : p<0.01), (**: p<0.05)(,)^{ns}: No significant.

Discussion and conclusions

The specie *Colchicum kotschyi* and *Stachys inflata* canopy cover, production and density from Liliaceae and Lamiaceae families and *Iris songarica* canopy cover (Iridaceae) increased in wildlife grazing site, but *Artemisia sieberi* and *Scorzonera sp.* canopy cover (Compositae) raised in livestock grazing area. The reason of decreasing these shrub species and increasing all species belong to the mentioned families can be deer food preference in comparison to sheep and goat. Deer graze these species more than livestock and cause decreasing shrubs. According to some researches, deer prefer shrub species more than other life forms (Moser & Witmer, 2000; Pellerin *et al.*, 2006; Bagheri *et al.*, 2008). Livestock use forbs better than other life forms and it can be a reason for a significant reduction in *Stachys inflata* parameters in livestock site. Firinioglu *et al.* (2007) and Heidarian Aghakhani *et al.* (2010) studies results confirmed this issue. In addition, deer grazing site condition secure these species ecological requires, spreading and reproduction of the species increase (Akbarzadeh *et al.*, 2007). Raising *Artemisia sieberi* canopy cover percentage can also

be an index to show more degradation of livestock grazing site and approximate resistance of this species to grazing (Jauffret & Lavorel, 2003; Navarro *et al.*, 2006).

The results showed that *Aegopordon berardioides*, *Scorzonera sp.* increase significantly in livestock grazing site. Some species like *Scorzonera sp.* and *Aegopordon berardioides* have different strategies as resistant species to grazing. For example, they partly protect themselves from grazing with expanding and sticking the leaves to the ground surface (Akbarzadeh *et al.*, 2007). This can be the reason for increasing them in livestock site. *Stipa barbata* canopy cover (Gramineae) also had a significant raise in livestock grazing area, because this species final bud is on the soil surface and grazing pressure injuries is less than other plants. This has been demonstrated through Louhaichi *et al.* (2012) research.

Most of species related to Compositae family are thorny and non-palatable. Increasing the number of Compositae family species in livestock grazing site can be the reason of more degradation and grazing pressure. Vakili *et al.* (2001) and Khosravi *et al.* (2010) announced that the presence of Compositae family species can be related to the utilization conditions.

According to results, it is necessary to recognize all aspects and details about vegetation in rangelands specially the specific plant species in order to proper grazing management and decide for future restoration planning.

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